

Data Management Plan for the Development of an Entanglement-Based Quantum Network with Quantum Repeaters

Version 1

Description

This data management plan outlines the strategy for managing, storing, and sharing data generated in the postdoc project with the No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/287 "The Development of Entanglement-Based Quantum Network with Quantum Repeaters (EQNET)." The plan details the types of entanglement network simulation data to be collected, the formats for storing data, codes, and other relevant data arising from the project implementation. The scientific objective of this

project is to investigate state-of-the-art quantum network architectures and quantum repeaters and combine them

into entanglement distribution network connecting two quantum computers in Helsinki, Finland and

Poznan, Poland through the Baltic states of Estonia, Latvia, and Lithuania. Planned project actions include

theoretical research on quantum network technological design requirements, current solutions, available devices

and developing a simulation model of the proposed network. Expected result is a model of a quantum network

capable of entanglement sharing using current quantum repeater device prototypes. EQNET project will have an

impact on the overall research sector locally, support the Latvian RIS3 strategy and National Development

Plan 2027, and contribute to the Quantum Internet Alliance (QIA) vision of a Europe-wide quantum network

through collaboration between European research and industry organizations.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Development of Entanglement-Based Quantum Network with Quantum Repeaters (EQNET)

Researchers

Rihards Murnieks (0000-0003-2034-9499)

Organizations

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Data Management Plan for the Development of an Entanglement-Based Quantum Network with Quantum Repeaters](#)

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Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grants: Development of Entanglement-Based Quantum Network with Quantum Repeaters (EQNET)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2025-12-22

4. Templates

Descriptions

Fidelity of entangled links between two end-nodes in quantum entanglement network in Latvia based on abstract quantum memory module

This dataset contains entangled link fidelity obtained in NetSquid simulation for the connection between two end-nodes in a 280 km-long quantum entanglement distribution network based on abstract quantum repeater nodes using NV-centre relaxation and coherence times. Data are obtained in two scenarios - using single-click and double-click

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DOI: - 22/12/2025

entanglement distribution protocols in two network topologies resulting from the real-world fiber grid limitations

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Data is collected to compare two quantum entanglement network topologies using two different entanglement distribution protocols and identify which network topology and protocol combination provides the best quality of service to be further used as the main topology for the quantum entanglement network in Latvia.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Textual data
- Other

Computer-generated data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

TXT

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

This data might be helpful for researchers working on quantum entanglement network research, and potentially for service providers to estimate the entangled link quality of service

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until the scientific article is published

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

GitHub

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

A text reader is required

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Rihards Murnieks (0000-0003-2034-9499)

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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